

Derivation of Feynman Propagator Using Cauchy's Residue Theorem of a Dirac Delta Driven Wave Equation.

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Abstract

The Green's Function of a Dirac Delta Driven Wave Equation was obtained after applying Cauchy's Residue Theorem to a contour integral. Solutions were obtained for initial conditions $t < 0$ and $t > 0$ by Fourier transforming the Green's function, obtaining preferred spatial variables of the Fourier transform, and inverse Fourier transforming back to a Green's function. Contour integrals were set up, prior to their evaluation the simple poles of the complex function were translated off the Real axis. Two contour integrals were evaluated, and the derived retarded Green's function: from initial condition $t < 0$ and advanced Green's function: from initial condition $t > 0$, represent a Feynman Propagator, an amplitude probability function used frequently in Quantum Field Theory.

Background

Green's Function Definition and Application

Considering a linear differential operator $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}(x)$ acting on generalized functions over some subset, ϱ , of \mathbb{R}^n , a Green's function $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{G}(x, s)$ at a point, $s \in \varrho$, corresponding to \mathcal{L} , is any solution of,

$$\mathcal{L}\mathcal{G}(x, s) = \mathcal{G}(x - s).$$

Where δ represents a delta function. Qualitatively, the Green's function is the solution to a differential equation containing a driving term provided through a point source. When considering *any* forcing term, the solution can be provided through an integration of the Green's function against the forcing term. [1]

$$u(x) = \int \mathcal{G}(x, s)f(s)ds$$

It is important to note that Green's functions are not "functions" by definition, but rather, distributions, hence the ability to integrate them against a function.

Nonhomogeneous linear ordinary differential equations of the general form [2] containing a delta function driving term, δ , can be solved with relative convenience via the Green's Function.¹

$$y^{(n)} = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \vartheta_i(x)y^{(i)} + \zeta(x) \quad ; \quad \zeta(x) \neq 0 \quad [2]$$

This, however, is one of many applications of the Green's function, as simpler initial condition and boundary value systems can be solved using this technique as well. The adaptability of Green's function has resulted in its uses across the spectrum of applied mathematics; with utilizations in Quantum Field Theory (QFT), Electrodynamics, and Statistical Field Theory. More specifically, in QFT, causal Green's functions are known as propagators, and give the probability amplitude of a particle traveling from one spatial point to another at distinct times.²

Contour Integration Definition and Application

In complex analysis, a contour is defined as a curve in the complex plane. Contour integration for continuous complex functions lying on smooth curves is analogous to the line integral for real valued functions. A precise mathematical definition is provided as follows for any continuous function:

$$f(t) = u(t) + iv(t) ; t \in \mathbb{R} \tag{3a}$$

$$f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{C} \tag{3b}$$

Then,

$$\int_a^b f(t)dt = \int_a^b (u(t) + iv(t))dt = \int_a^b u(t)dt + i \int_a^b v(t)dt \tag{4}$$

Let $f: \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ be continuous on the directed smooth curve, μ , and let $z: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ be a parametrization consistent with its direction. Then,

$$\int_{\mu} f(z)dz = \int_a^b f(\mu(t))\mu'(t)dt \tag{5}$$

There are various methods to calculate the contour integral, as seen above, contour parameterization using a differentiable complex-valued function with real variables with subsequent integrand parametrization and evaluation of the resulting real-valued integral proves to be the most consistent and effective. However, consistency does not correspond to simplicity, and direct evaluation tends to be difficult. Contour integration becomes incredibly powerful with appropriate application of Cauchy's Residue Theorem or the Cauchy Integral Formula. Both techniques can greatly simplify integrals and provide precise solutions to those once considered solvable through numerical means only.⁵

Cauchy's Residue Theorem Definition

Consider a holomorphic function $f(z)$ with a finite number of simple poles at $z = z_i$, where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Define a closed curve, β , in a subset, \mathcal{U} , of \mathbb{C} . Then, the line integral of $f(z)$ about β is equal to $2\pi i$ times the sum of residues of $f(z = z_i)$,⁴

$$\oint_{\beta} f(z) dz = 2\pi i \sum \text{Res}(f(z = z_i)) \tag{6}$$

Fourier Transform

The Fourier Transform, FT, of a signal function, f ,

$$F(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) e^{-j\omega t} dt \quad [7a]$$

Where F is a real variable complex valued function. The Inverse Fourier Transform can then be defined as,

$$f(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(\omega) e^{-j\omega t} dt \quad [7b]$$

Briefly, the FT distills a signal function into its component frequencies, the absolute value of the FT provides the frequency value of the original function.⁶

In this paper, techniques of contour integration, specifically Cauchy's Residue Theorem, will be applied to the Wave Equation to obtain the retarded Green's functions and advanced Green's function. These solutions are known as the Feynman propagators found in QFT. It is important to note that there are many other, simpler techniques, to obtain the Green's function, including Eigenvector expansion.

Deriving Feynman Propagator of Wave Equation

Outline of Technique

First, the Green's function is obtained, and Fourier transformed, the differential operator is then applied to the Fourier transform, which will contain a set of simple poles. The Green's function is then reobtained in preferred position variables using the inverse Fourier transform. Contour integration is performed using the simple poles of the inverse Fourier transform, and a solution for the initial conditions is then obtained. Explicit conditions are evaluated to then derive specific Green's functions.

Derivation

Consider a wave equation when sourced by a delta function with respect to space, r , and time, t , the Green's Function, \mathcal{G} , is defined as.

$$(-\nabla^2 + c^{-2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}) \mathcal{G}(r, t; r', t') = 4\pi \delta^3(r - r') \delta(t - t') \quad [8]$$

Translation invariance allows $r' = 0, t' = 0$,

$$(-\nabla^2 + c^{-2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}) \mathcal{G}(r, t; r', t') = 4\pi \delta^3(r) \delta(t) \quad [9]$$

Setting $c = 1$ to be substituted later, and specifying the Fourier transform of \mathcal{G} as,

$$\mathcal{G}(r, t) = 2\pi^{-s-1} \int \zeta^s k d\varpi e^{i(kr-wt)} g(k, \varpi) \quad [10]$$

Thus,

$$g(k, \varpi) = \int \zeta^s r dt e^{i(kr-wt)} \mathcal{G}(r, t) \quad [11]$$

It follows from the Fourier transform of [6] that,

$$(k^2 - \varpi^2) g(k, \varpi) = 4\pi \quad [12]$$

Thus,

$$\mathcal{G}(r, t) = 2\pi^{-s-1} \int \zeta^s k d\varpi e^{i(kr-wt)} \frac{4\pi}{(k^2 - \varpi^2)} \quad [13]$$

In order to evaluate this as a contour integral, the poles on Re (shown below) at $\varpi = \pm k$ must be shifted using $i\epsilon$, such that $\varpi = \pm k - i\epsilon$. Adjusting [13] gives,

$$\tilde{\mathcal{G}}(r, t) = 2\pi^{-1} \int \zeta^s k d\varpi e^{i(kr-wt)} \frac{4\pi}{k^2 - (\varpi + i\epsilon)^2} \quad [14]$$

The following pole shift is visualized below [Figure 1], with $t < 0$ per initial conditions. The integral is bound at $\varpi = \pm R\epsilon$, constituting a semicircle in the upper half of the plane.

Figure 1

The integral, \mathcal{J} , is then,

$$\mathcal{J} \equiv \oint d\varpi e^{-i\omega t} \frac{1}{k^2 - (\varpi + i\epsilon)^2} = \tilde{\mathcal{G}}(k, t) + \int_R \frac{1}{k^2 - (\varpi + i\epsilon)^2} \quad [15]$$

$$\text{Taking } \lim_{R \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{J}, \text{ such that } \mathcal{J} = 2\pi i \cdot \sum \text{Res}(\varpi = \pm k - i\epsilon)$$

$\sum \text{Res}(\varpi = \pm k - i\epsilon)$ exists outside the bounds of the contour, $\mathcal{J} = 0$, so $\tilde{\mathcal{G}}(k, t) = 0$ for all $t < 0$.

Evaluating now for $t > 0$, the contour is closed about the lower half plane [Figure 2], in this case, poles do exist within the contour, that is $\sum Res(\varpi = \pm k - i\epsilon)$ exists within the bounds of the contour.

Figure 2

Thus, this integral, \mathcal{J} , is equal to,

$$\mathcal{J} = -2\pi i \cdot \sum Res(\varpi = \pm k - i\epsilon) = -2\pi i \cdot \left(i \frac{\sin kt}{k}\right) \quad [16]$$

For $t > 0$,

$$\tilde{\mathcal{G}}(k, t) = 2\pi \frac{\sin kt}{k} \quad [17]$$

And,

$$\mathcal{G}(r, t) = 2\pi^{-\zeta} \int \zeta^\zeta k d\varpi e^{ikr} \frac{4\pi}{k} \sin kt \quad [18]$$

Thus, we have obtained a $\mathcal{G}(r, t)$ that is a satisfactory solution to the wave equation with the initial condition, $\mathcal{G} = 0$ for negative t , also known as the retarded Green's function. We have also obtained the advanced Green's function, that is, the solution satisfying the initial conditions for which t is positive. \mathcal{G} is colloquially known as a Feynman propagator, and is always obtained when taking a contour going over a right pole and under a left pole.

Lastly, we must evaluate this integral for explicit conditions, ζ , to explicitly obtain a Green's function,

For $\zeta = 3$;

$$\mathcal{G}(r, t) = 2\pi^{-3} \int k^2 dk d\cos \theta d\phi e^{ikr \cos \theta} \frac{4\pi}{k} \sin kt \quad [19]$$

Performing the integral over $\cos \theta$,

$$\mathcal{G}(r, t) = \frac{2}{\pi r} \int_0^\infty \sin kt \sin kr \, dk \quad [20]$$

$$= \frac{1}{2\pi r} \int_{-\infty}^\infty [\cos(kr - kt) - \cos(kr + kt)] \, dk \quad [21]$$

$$= \frac{1}{r} [\delta(r - t) - \delta(r + t)] \quad [22]$$

Recall,

$$\delta(\xi) = \begin{cases} 0, & \xi \neq 0 \\ \infty, & \xi = 0 \end{cases} \quad [23]$$

Since $t, r > 0$,

$$\mathcal{G}(r, t) = \frac{1}{r} \delta\left(t - \frac{r}{c}\right) \quad [24]$$

Now considering the 2nd condition $\zeta = 2$,

$$\mathcal{G}(r, t) = 2\pi^{-2} \int k \, dk \, d\theta \, e^{ikr \cos \theta} \frac{4\pi}{k} \sin kt \quad [25]$$

$$= \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \, e^{iz \cos \theta} \quad [26]$$

Resulting in a Bessel function from the angular integral,

$$= 2 \int_0^\pi d\theta \, \cos(z \cos \theta) \quad [27]$$

$$= 2\pi \Gamma_0(z) \quad [28]$$

Hence, the Green's function for said conditions is defined by the improper antiderivative,

$$\mathcal{G}(r, t) = 2 \int_0^\infty dk \, \Gamma_0(kr) \sin kt \quad [29]$$

Recall,

$$\left(-\nabla^2 + c^{-2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}\right) \mathcal{G}(r, t; r', t') = 4\pi \zeta^{\zeta} (r - r') \delta(t - t') \quad [30]$$

With $\zeta = 3$, and an integration over z' :

$$(\Lambda)\mathcal{G}^{(2)}(x, y, t; x', y', t') = 4\pi\delta(x - x')\delta(y - y')\delta(t - t') \quad [31a]$$

Where,

$$\Lambda = -\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \quad [31b]$$

[31a] is then,

$$\left(-\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}\right)\mathcal{G}^{(2)}(x, y, t; x', y', t') = 4\pi\delta(x - x')\delta(y - y')\delta(t - t') \quad [32]$$

Defining $\mathcal{G}^{(2)}(x, y, t; x', y', t')$ as,

$$\mathcal{G}^{(2)}(x, y, t; x', y', t') = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dz' \mathcal{G}^{(3)}(r, t; r', t') \quad [33]$$

Λ disappears as $\mathcal{G}^{(2)}$ is independent of z . To perform the integral a cylindrical coordinate conversion must occur, that is $x^2 + y^2 = \rho^2$, with $t' = x' = y' = 0$.

Converting to cylindrical coordinates,

$$\mathcal{G}^{(2)}(x, y, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dz' \frac{1}{\sqrt{\rho^2 + z'^2}} \delta(t - \sqrt{\rho^2 + z'^2}) \quad [34]$$

Define the δ argument to be $f(z') = t - \sqrt{\rho^2 + z'^2}$, so

$$f'(z') = \frac{z'}{\sqrt{\rho^2 + z'^2}} = z'/t \quad [35]$$

The δ argument results in the imposition of $t = \sqrt{\rho^2 + z'^2}$ or $z' = \sqrt{t^2 - \rho^2}$ because,

$$\delta(\xi) = \begin{cases} 0, & \xi \neq 0 \\ \infty, & \xi = 0 \end{cases} \quad [36]$$

Resulting in,

$$\mathcal{G}^{(2)}(x, y, t) = z'^{-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{c^2 t^2 - \rho^2}} \quad [37]$$

Thus,

$$\mathcal{G}^{(2)}(x, y, t) = \begin{cases} z'^{-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{c^2 t^2 - \rho^2}} & \text{for } \rho < ct \\ 0 & \text{for } \rho > ct \end{cases} \quad [38]$$

Understanding the Feynman Propagator

Consider a particle propagating from one arbitrary point to another, to adhere to causality a “Time Ordering Operator” must be applied to the amplitude of propagation term describing this motion, this operator is known as the Feynman Propagator.⁷ The Feynman prescription, $i\epsilon$ (seen in derivation above), is added to prevent divergence of the integral thereon. It is important to note that the Feynman propagator is more than an abstract mathematical technique to avoid improper integral divergence; rather, it is an imposition of nature’s most profound immovable law, causality, to particles whose propagations would otherwise contradict the temporal component of Minkowski space. It is important to note, though, that the Feynman propagator can be dispensed with a symmetric approach under a set of well-defined conditions,⁸ a hesitant and yet reconfirmed hint at replaceability of one of QFT’s most important techniques.

There are other techniques available to obtain the Green’s function for the wave equation;³ the purpose of this derivation though, is not to provide the simplest, or quickest derivation of \mathcal{G} , rather, it is to highlight the effectiveness of the Residue Theorem and contour integration in solving difficult integrals. As seen in equations [15] and [16], integrals can be evaluated effortlessly with proper application of the theorem, that is, the effective summing of residues at the indicated simple poles. Systems that fail to meet the conditions for easier analytical techniques can always be evaluated using similar methods to what is seen above.

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